

ASSESSMENT OF AXIOLOGICAL POTENTIAL IN FUTURE TEACHERS AND THEIR INDICATORS

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ABSTRACT

In this article, in the education of a perfect person, based on life experiences, he entered the system of social sciences within the framework of phenomena that teach the laws, principles and methods of forming a high spiritual meaning, having its theoretical, national and practical foundations, theoretical foundations of pedagogy. It is based on the general rules and principles of education and training of a perfect person, relying on the rich experience created by the people, theoretical and methodical sources of scientific research, the works of enlightened thinkers of Central Asia and the world, aimed at human perfection. For this purpose, the national heritage of each nation is connected with universal, universal human values. In different periods of the development of the society, the conceptual foundations of family education were considered to be universal values, as well as the problems of forming such qualities as correctness, honor, dignity, kindness, humanity and hard work, and the ability to respond to kindness with kindness.

Keywords: axiological potential, teacher's value, information technologies in education, pedagogy.

INTRODUCTION

Educating a person in every way is the eternal dream of mankind, and our ancestors searched for ways and rules of how to teach enlightenment and culture to the young generation, to lead them to perfection. In fact, achieving enlightened and spiritual perfection of a person is carried out under the leadership of pedagogy. Pedagogy is the science of education. "Pedagogy" is a Greek word that means "pedagogos" – "child

leader”. The science of pedagogy gained its position among the people as a result of changes in people’s attitude towards spiritual and educational perfection. Thus, pedagogy, as a science that educates people, has taken a special place among the system of world sciences. The main issue of pedagogy is education. The broad meaning of education is education, development, bringing up a mature person in connection with information.

Axiology is the name of the “theory of value”. It is derived from the Greek word “axios” which means “value”. Formal axiology is a logic-based science of value based on a “hierarchy of meaning” from the most meaningful or richest value to the most destructive or the greatest loss of value. Logic defines 18 different wealth levels. Hartman’s “Hierarchy of Values” is a mathematical standard of measurement for human evaluation and decision-making in life and in all social spheres of life in our culture.

People use their mental and emotional capacities to make judgments about their worth. Some people have very strong and reliable decision -making skills, while others regularly make bad or wrong choices. Axiological profiles measure the quality of a respondent’s thinking and decision-making by measuring their mental clarity and emotional orientation and conditioning.

Activity in the educational process leads the student to deep and solid acquisition of knowledge, to demonstrate his abilities. Activity to knowledge ensures the intellectual development of the student.

The basis of activity is always need. The variety of needs also expands the types of activities. Accordingly, their activities are different at different age periods of the student. In an educational institution, the same requirement all the time does not give a positive result in the development of a person. The types and nature of activities should change in different age periods.

APPLICATION OF AXIOLOGICAL VIEWS IN EDUCATION

A person’s social activity and ability is the guarantee of all his success. Because every person becomes active only with his own work, enthusiasm, and desire. No matter how well the teacher teaches or educates, if the student himself does not try, the development will not be successful. After all, the main reason for all spiritual and moral deficiencies is that a person does not manage his activities in the right way.

That is why human activity is also the result of its development. Therefore, it is important to develop the qualities of social activity, initiative, creativity on the basis of individual activity - to develop the activity through the manifestation of personal potential.

The general tasks of secondary special vocational education are as follows:

- satisfying the national-cultural needs of the population, raising a physically and spiritually healthy generation [1];
- to ensure that students master the system of knowledge determined by social and production requirements [2];
- formation of scientific outlook, political, economic, legal culture, creative, free thinking skills in them, increasing their independent knowledge [3];
- love for the Motherland, patriotism, civic outlook, human dignity, participation in democratic self-management, as well as responsibility for one's own actions in young people [4].

These general tasks consist of a number of separate issues. They are combined in the content of academic subjects.

Types and forms of education. Types of education in European and Eastern, Asian and American countries have arisen as a result of historical development. The first type is mythological education, in which the essence of the world is studied in the form of fairy tales, legends, epics, short stories and songs [5].

The next historical type was scholastic education. According to its essence, in education, knowledge about text culture and knowledge about the earth and sky is expressed in words, on the basis of training memory and will, the young generation is given knowledge about human existence and the content of activities organized by it, literacy and speech culture are taught..

The third historical type of education is the Enlightenment, which arose during the creation of worldly knowledge. Since the 20th century, the process of development of different educational paradigms (models), types and forms has been observed.

Today, there are the following types and forms of teaching the basics:

1. According to the type and quality of acquiring scientific knowledge (biological, mathematical, physical, economic, philological education, etc.);
2. According to priority content (theoretical and practical, humanitarian, etc.);
3. According to the type and skill of acquiring social activities (musical, artistic, technical, technological, pedagogical-medical education, etc.);
4. According to the acquisition of cultural values (traditional education, artistic-aesthetic, religious education, etc.);
5. According to the scale of human society's assimilation of cultural values (national, European, international, global education, etc.);
6. According to the type of educational system (university, academic, gymnasium, lyceum education, etc.);
7. According to the priority of the direction of educational content (formal and material, scientific and elementary, humanitarian and natural sciences, general secondary, specialized secondary, vocational, higher, etc.);

8. According to the level of education (primary, partial secondary, general secondary, specialized secondary, vocational, higher education.

The content of education is a model of the social order that reflects the social experience and culture of the society, the demands placed on the level of spiritual development of the individual[6].

Social experience is characterized by the following four elements:

- human knowledge about nature, society;
- skills, competences and methods of activity;
- experience of creative activity in solving new tasks;
- the experience of mutual emotional (emotional)-valuable relationships with others.

Accordingly, according to the ideas of modern didactics, the content of education reflects the following: 1) knowledge about the world ; 2) experience of activity implementation methods; 3) experience of creative activity; 4) experience of emotional-valuable attitude to the environment [7].

The main factors determining the content of education will be:

1. The degree of development of science, technology, culture in society;
2. Goals and objectives of education;
3. Age characteristics of students;
4. The needs of the learner personality.

Currently, there are different approaches to understanding the essence of education. That is:

1. According to the sociological approach, the essence of education is to convey social experiences to young people. Pupils learn knowledge that is the result of the socio-historical experience of mankind. The content of education is to organize a process that serves students to master the experience of their ancestors. This rule implies a scientific approach to the understanding of an important factor of socio-historical development - the maturity of a person.

2. The special pedagogical or didactic approach represents the stages of learning (studying the educational material, understanding it, strengthening it, applying knowledge in practical activities) that determine the progress of the overall educational process. According to this approach, the content of education consists in organizing activities based on following the sequence of stages of knowledge acquisition by students.

3. The psychological approach is associated with the creation of LSVygotsky's (1896-1934) view that education is the main factor in the development of a person, which is called the "zone of proximal development". According to him, education becomes meaningful only when it is built in the immediate zone, when it is based on

mechanical actions that are not yet fully formed, but can be the basis for building the educational process.

4. The dialectical approach is based on the philosophical doctrine that illuminates the general laws regarding the movement and development of nature, society and thinking. According to him, the educational process should allow the human mind to reflect existence. Knowing the truth is a complex process. According to the idea of a dialectical approach, the basis of development is opposition. Development is a struggle of opposing forces.

According to the dialectical approach, the main contradictions of the educational process are listed as follows:

1. Contrast between the amount of socio-historical (scientific) knowledge and the amount of knowledge acquired by the student. This contradiction is the driving force of the educational process. It leads to continuous improvement of educational content. The need to bring general secondary and secondary special vocational education closer to the level of socio-technical development makes it an important social task to fundamentally update the content of education, search for new principles, forms, methods and tools.

2. The contradiction between the level of the student's knowledge and the form, methods and tools that he should acquire. The resolution of this contradiction depends on the pace and level of the student's intellectual development. Educational material of the same content and volume can be manifested by different indicators of mental development.

3. The contrast between the student's current level of development and the level of development envisaged by the social order. If the social demand is higher than the child's ability to perceive, then a serious difficulty arises.

5. Axiological (from the Greek "axios" - valuable, logia - science) approach is a philosophical doctrine about values, according to which, during the educational process, the student learns about life, health, love, family, education, work, peace, trust, beauty, creativity, humanity and should be introduced to such values.

Laws and principles of education. All laws applicable in the educational process are divided into two groups according to their general and special character. Laws that cover the entire didactic system according to their application are called general, and laws that apply only to individual components are called special [8].

The laws of education are as follows: 1) existence of interrelationship between educational factors, conditions and results; 2) the connection of the educational process with social factors and the needs of society; 3) mutual unity of education, development and upbringing; 4) the requirement of interaction between the teacher, student and studied objects in any educational process; 5) ensuring the effectiveness of the

educational process based on the educational activity shown by students; 6) formation of skills as a result of regular and repeated repetition of certain operations and actions; 7) that the thoroughness of mastering depends on the consistency of repetition; 8) that the complex methods of activity mastered by students are the result of the teacher's successful mastering of the simplest methods of activity.

AGE AND SPECIFIC CHARACTERISTICS OF DEVELOPMENT

Anatomical, physiological (physical) and psychological characteristics characteristic of a certain age period are called age characteristics. Education and training work is organized taking into account these young characteristics. Then the influence of education on the child's development will be strong.

It is important to know and take into account the characteristics of different age periods in the child's development in order to have a proper approach to children's education and to teach it successfully. Because the growth and development of the child's organism and mental development are different at different ages. Abu Ali Ibn Sina, Yan Amos Comensky, KDUshinsky, Abdullah Awlani also emphasized the need to educate a child [9].

In his book *The New Science of Axiological Psychology* (Pomeroy, 2005), Dr. Leon Pomeroy has shown that formal axiology also has an empirical basis. Thus, in our axiological evaluation profiles, we strongly support both scientific methods: the axiomatic method based on deductive logic and the inductive, empirical method. Dr. Pomeroy spent more than 20 years collecting statistics for his book in different countries, from many and varied eastern and western countries and cultures, and to prove that cultures all over the world value the same [10].

Neuro-axiology: Combines neuroscience's understanding of how the brain works with the formal science of axiology, which provides an objective measure of how people judge value. (You always choose what you think is MOST VALUABLE in your life.) Accepting the standard of the neuroscientific model of consciousness means that everything we think, feel, remember, and do is a function of the brain. This includes empathy. We are not empaths because it makes sense to be empathetic, which is that most people simply do not think in a way to empathize. We simply do not learn empathy (although brain development is an interactive process with the environment, so we cannot rule out environmental influences). Most of the time, we have empathy because our brains are wired for empathy as a specific function [11].

As with every bodily function you can think of, if it is not necessary for survival, some part of the human population may have that function impaired or even absent. We think of the biological limits of empathy or the lack of empathy as a disorder, psychopathy. It is estimated that about 1% of the general population are psychopaths,

and about 20-30% in US prisons. Dr. Robert S. Hartman found that people retain a 40% hidden reserve of cooperation and productivity until they are valued as human beings.

Axiology is the science of how people value and evaluate values, and how they relate to morality (moral values are often not related to religion or culture).

The foundations of axiology are found in its 3 value classes and 6 “counselors”. The following are value classes:

- Systematic: plans, rules, best practices, procedures; ideas or expectations
- External: practical or situational; measurable, observable; duties (material)
- Intrinsic: personal or transcendent; infinitely valuable; irreplaceable; people (intangibles)

Below are 6 advisors, consisting of 2 opinions, one internal and one external, and remember that people are neither their opinions nor their advisors.

- Viewing the world: Empathy-intuition “people”, Practical judgment “tasks and systematic thinking” “plans and ideas”

- Self-concept: Self-esteem is “who you are”, role awareness is “what you do”, and self-direction is “where you’re going”.

The problems of axiology fall into four main groups, namely (1) the nature of value, (2) types of value, (3) the criterion of value, and (4) the metaphysical status of value.

The nature of value experience. Evaluation is the fulfillment of desire (voluntarism: Spinoza, Ehrenfels), pleasure (hedonism: Epicurus, Bentham, Meinong), interest (Perry), preference (Martineau), purely rational will (formalism: Stoics, Kant, Royce), third-order consciousness. qualities (Santayana), the synoptic experience of the unity of personality (personalism: TH Green, Bowne), any experience that contributes to the improvement of life (evolution: Nietzsche), or “the relation of things to ends or consequences actually achieved” (pragmatism, instrumentalism: Dewey).

Value types. Most axiologists distinguish between intrinsic (consumer) values that are valued for themselves and instrumental (contributory) values (means) that are the causes of intrinsic values (either as economic goods or natural phenomena). Most intrinsic values are also important for appreciating the experience; some instrumental values are neutral or even intrinsically devalued. A few recognized as intrinsic values (moral) are good, true, beautiful, and holy. The values of play, work, association and physical well-being are also recognized. Some (with Montague) question whether truth is to be taken as a proper value, since some truths are worthless, and some neutral; but the love of truth, regardless of consequences, seems to establish the value of truth. There is disagreement about whether the sacred (religious value) is a specific type (Schleiermacher, Otto) or a relation to other values (Kant, Höffding) or a combination

of both (Hawking). There is disagreement about whether the diversity of values is irreducible (pluralism) or whether all values are rationally related in a hierarchy or system (Plato, Hegel, Sorley), in which values penetrate or merge into a shared experience.

Value criterion. The standard of value testing is influenced by both psychological and logical theory. Hedonists find the standard in the amount of pleasure obtained by an individual (Aristippus) or society (Bentham). Intuitionists refer to the ultimate concept of preference (Martineau, Brentano). Some idealists recognize an objective system of rational norms or ideals as a criterion (Plato, Windelband), while others emphasize rational integrity and consistency (Hegel, Bosanquet, Paton) or inclusiveness (TH Green). Naturalists consider biological survival or adaptation (Dewey) as standard. Despite the differences, the results of applying these criteria have much in common.

The metaphysical state of value. What is the relationship of values to the facts studied by natural science (Kehler), from Sein to Sollen (Lotze, Rickert), value experience to reality independent of man (Hegel, Pringle-Pattleson, Spaulding)? There are three main answers: subjectivism (value depends entirely on and relative to human experience: hence most hedonists, naturalists, positivists); logical objectivism (values are a logical essence or being that is independent of being known, but has no existential status or action in reality); metaphysical objectivism (values - or norms or ideals - are integral, objective and active components of metaphysical reality: so theists, absolutists and some realists and naturalists, such as S. Alexander and Wiman).

Is very difficult to take into account the unique nature of the child. Because children of the same age can be mentally different.

For example, vision and hearing, activity, quick perception, slow thinking, impulsiveness or restraint, eloquence or lack of eloquence, enthusiasm or lack of enthusiasm, laziness or industriousness, clumsiness or indolence, compactness or lack of work. quick access, ability, etc., are effects of the nervous system, and the teacher or educator must know them.

In order to know the individual characteristics of the child, it is important to know the general types of temperament and the methodology of studying the characteristics of the child.

There are also specific developmental patterns of different age periods. For example, 5th graders and 10th graders cannot be equated. Therefore, the child's physical and mental maturity is divided into periods in Table 1.

Table 1. Physical and mental development of the child

No	period	Age
1	Infancy	the period from the end of infancy (1 month) to the age of one year.
2	Pre-kindergarten age	From 1 to 3 years.
3	Preschool education age	From 3 to 7 years.
4	Pupils of junior school age	7-11-12 years old.
5	High school age students (teenagers)	14-15 years old.
6	High school students (teenagers)	16-18 years old.

It can be said that among the problems in the formation and development of competence of teachers in the field of ICT, the development of pedagogically based methods of using hardware tools lags far behind their development. In order for hardware and software tools to become the main weapon of a teacher in an educational institution, the future teacher should acquire this tool and the methodology of its use in a higher educational institution of pedagogy. For this, they need “Information technologies in education”, “Pedagogical software tools”, simulators, educational computer environments, creation of control (test) tasks, tools for automating the results of training quality control, statistical processing of training results. software tools etc. need to be taught more.

In the teacher’s subject “Learning to understand - what kind of ICT can and should be used in a specific situation?” it would be appropriate if this question became the main slogan.

Table 2. Reflexive criterion diagnostic methodical competencies and their indicators

The method of the teacher competence	Measurable indicators	Methods of measuring indicators
(cognitive) MK-1	Willingness to use knowledge about cultural structures in the process of professional activity. Pedagogical programming knowledge and readiness to use their core foundation in building a school informatics course, organizing it based on communications, and solving programming.	educational project. Informatics teacher - expert evaluation of the head of pedagogical practice of students.
(constructive - prognostic) MK-2	Competence of planning, sorting, synthesizing and designing computer-related material. Knowing and being able to design students’ activities taking into account their individual characteristics.	Evaluation of the educational project. Expert assessment of methodical science teachers.
(organizational - technological) MK-3	ability to determine specific goals of education, to choose adequate, including innovative forms, methods and tools of computer science education. The ability to organize students’ activities, including on the Internet, as well as their extracurricular work on the implementation of computer science co-curricular projects.	Knowledgeable __ t e st b a h o l a sh. Teacher of informatics - teacher of pedagogical practice of students e xp e rt assessment.

		Monitoring students' performance of collaborative learning projects.
(information - communicative) MK-4	Analysis of information mastering the methods of doing, comparing and understanding. Determining the reliability of the material. Knowing the types of electronic educational resources and using them in the practice of teaching computer science. Students' knowledge of ICT content and application technologies as a means of forming universal learning activities in students.	Completing the control task. Evaluation of the educational project. Test assessment of knowledge. Informatics teacher - expert evaluation of the head of pedagogical practice of students. Assessment of knowledge test.
(control-evaluation) MK-5	Knowledge and application of different methods of diagnosis using ICT, including levels of education of students in informatics.	Knowledgeable _ _ t e s t b a h o l a s h. E x p e r t assessment of teachers of methodological subjects.
(reflexive - analytical) MK-6	Self-knowledge, self-improvement, self - evaluation	Methods of measuring indicators.

Universal truths are that there is no such thing as mere rape, involuntary torture considered honorable, and the inhumane abuse of innocents. You sorry offer to do possible, however real values violation it is true. Axiologists aesthetic values, morals values and epistemic values own into received all value forms with wide they are engaged. Thor meaning, axiologists from himself valuable or worth it thing - by itself not a slave was things with they are engaged. All axiological issues are necessarily related to ontological and epistemological assumptions. Axiologists are broadly concerned with all forms of value, including aesthetic values, moral values, and epistemic values. Narrowly speaking, axiologists are concerned with what is valuable or worthwhile in and of itself - what is desirable in and of itself. All axiological issues are necessarily related to ontological and epistemological assumptions. Axiologists are broadly concerned with all forms of value, including aesthetic values, moral values, and epistemic values. Narrowly speaking, axiologists are concerned with what is valuable or worthwhile in and of itself - what is desirable in and of itself. All axiological issues are necessarily related to ontological and epistemological assumptions.

CONCLUSION

Axiological ethics can be seen as an application of ethics, referring to naturalistic views of ethics based on a rational and empirical examination of the natural world. Scientists who use neuropsychology and metaphysical naturalism together with axiomatic values as “first principles” can define the universal foundations of morality. Society should consider normative ethics as a field of science, the goal of which is the pursuit of prosperity. Axiologists tried to describe the concept of general value, which

is only one type of moral value. They argue, against Kant, that goodness does not derive from the will alone, but exists in objective hierarchies.

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